

TRANSMISSION ELECTRON MICROSCOPY CHARACTERIZATION OF EFFECT OF GRAPHITE IN ZrB₂-BASED COMPOSITES

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Abstract

The effect of graphite flake on the microstructure of ZrB₂-SiC composite was investigated by transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and the comparative analysis of its influence on the mechanical properties reported in literatures also has been done. ZrB₂-20 vol. % SiC (ZS) and ZrB₂-20 vol. % SiC-15 vol. % graphite (ZSG) composites were prepared from commercially available powders by hot-pressed sintering method. In ZrB₂-SiC composite, many stacking faults in SiC grains and lots of dislocations in ZrB₂ grains were observed by TEM due to the different temperature coefficients of thermal expansion. With the addition of graphite flake to the ZrB₂-SiC composite, fewer defects were observed in the grains around the graphite flake in the TEM micrograph. Moreover, the graphite flake produces bending in hot-pressed sintering process, while the stress is eased around the graphite flake in ZrB₂-SiC composites, which improve the mechanical properties of ZrB₂-SiC composite. Thus, the graphite flake plays a positive role in ZrB₂-SiC composite.

1. Introduction

ZrB₂-based composites have been regarded as promising for high temperature structural material applications because of their unique combination of high thermal shock resistance, high strength at elevated temperature and low density [1]. However, the low fracture toughness of ZrB₂-based composite is still a limiting factor to be used widely. Some additives were used to improve the mechanical properties.

The addition of SiC particles controls the growth of ZrB₂ grain, and gets an achievement of full density [2] which improves their oxidation resistance and mechanical properties. Sumin Zhu al. has studied the influence of size of SiC particle on the mechanical properties of ZrB₂ [15]. They found

the strength increased as the size of SiC particles decreased.

Some studies have shown that the introduction of graphite improves the fracture toughness and resistance to slow crack growth. The literature has reported that the fracture toughness of ZrB₂-SiC-graphite is $6.1 \pm 0.3 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, which is much higher than that of ZrB₂-SiC composite [4]. Zhi Wang al. has studied the effect of graphite on thermal shock behavior of ZrB₂-SiC composite [5].

Graphite is a crystalline form of elemental carbon. In each carbon layer, graphite has carbon sp² hybridization with covalent bonding, which has extremely high strength, stiffness and thermal conductivity along the basal plane [6]. These layers are bonded by weak van der Waals forces [7]. This layered structure provides a mechanism of self-lubrication. The introduction of Graphite flake to ZrB₂-based composite promotes the grain refining and densification [8]. To evaluate the properties of microstructure of composite, many approaches were applied, such as optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Because of the brittleness of the ZrB₂-SiC-graphite, few reports appear in literature to analysis the microstructures by TEM. In this paper, we have investigated the microstructures of ZrB₂-SiC and ZrB₂-SiC-graphite composite by transmission electron microscopy equipped with an energy-dispersive X-ray system.

Transmission electron microscopy is a very important technique to characterize the microstructures of ceramic materials. The information of materials could be studied by conventional imaging, electron diffraction and chemical microanalysis-EDX got by TEM. The major contribution of TEM is the enlarged understanding of materials [9], for instance, E.J. Olivier and J.H. Neethling [10] have investigated the defects of stacking faults and twins in β -SiC by TEM. Takashi Mizuguchi and Shuqi Guo have

characterized the spark plasma sintered ZrB_2 ceramic by TEM [11]. Jun Liang al. [12] has researched the characterization of interface of Zr_2 -SiC by TEM. Tao Zhu al. [13] analyzed the additives in TEM micrographs of ZrB_2 -SiCw composite

This paper focuses on microstructures of ZrB_2 -SiC and ZrB_2 -SiC-graphite composite based on transmission electron microscopy. The images of the microstructure of the ceramic got by TEM and their mechanical properties reported in the literature [2] were compared, and the effect of graphite flake in the ZrB_2 -based composite was also analyzed.

2. Experimental

ZrB_2 -20 vol. % SiC mixture and ZrB_2 -20 vol. % SiC-15 vol. % graphite mixture were prepared respectively from commercially available powders. Commercially available ZrB_2 powder (2 μm , > 99.5%, Northwest Institute for non-ferrous metal research, China), SiC (1 μm , > 99.5%, Weifang Kaihua Micro-powder Co., Ltd., China.) and the graphite flake (mean diameter and thickness are 15 μm and 1.5 μm , respectively, > 99%, Qingdao Tiansheng Graphite Co., Ltd., China) were used as raw powders in this study. The two kinds of mixtures (ZrB_2 + 20 vol. % SiC and ZrB_2 + 20 vol. % SiC + 15 vol. % graphite flake) were ball-mixed for 10 h in a polyethylene bottle using ZrO_2 balls and ethanol as the grinding media respectively. After mixing, the slurry was dried in a rotary evaporator and screened. The powder was put into a graphite die and sintered by hot pressing at 1900 $^{\circ}C$ for 1 h under a uniaxial load of 30 MPa in Ar atmosphere. Then the microstructural feature of the hot pressed composite was observed by Transmission electron microscopy equipped with an energy-dispersive X-ray system.

The thin specimen preparation for TEM was quite difficult, because the ZrB_2 -based composite is brittle and the graphite flakes tend to fall during the procedures of grinding and polishing. The specimens for TEM observation were prepared from hot pressed material in our research, which is different from that of the former study (the powder mixtures sintered by SPS used to replace the materials consolidated by hot-pressing were investigated by TEM [14]). The TEM samples were cut into discs with diameter of 5 mm and a thickness of 1 mm by optical methods. Then the discs were milled down to a thickness of 100 μm by hand. Because of the brittleness of the ceramics, they could not be cut too thin. The small discs were further ion beam thinned

with low angle until small perforations were observed by optical microscopy. The phase analysis of the ceramic was performed using transmission electron microscopy (TEM, Tecnai G2F30) equipped with an energy-dispersive X-ray system. The crystal structure analysis of the ZrB_2 -based ceramics was identified by selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns. And Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) was used to determine the composition inside the grains during TEM observation.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Microstructure of ZrB_2 -SiC

TEM micrograph of different phases and the interfaces of ZrB_2 -SiC composite was shown in Fig.1. EDX spectra of the two grains in the image (marked A and B) are shown in Fig.2 and Fig.3. From the EDX spectra, A and B indicate ZrB_2 and SiC respectively. The generation of contrast depends on the atomic number of the phases. ZrB_2 with high atomic number is darker than SiC in the TEM micrograph of ZrB_2 -SiC. And the grains show equiaxed shape. The ZrB_2 /SiC and ZrB_2 / ZrB_2 grain boundaries are very clean with no impurities (Fig.1). Our research enjoys the same result as J. Zou analysed by HRTEM [8]. There is no chemical reaction between ZrB_2 and SiC grains at boundaries in the hot-pressing process.

Fig.1. TEM micrograph of ZrB_2 -SiC composite

Fig.2. The EDX spectra of A grain in Fig.1

Fig.3. The EDX spectra of B grain in Fig.1

The phases of the ZrB₂ and SiC were confirmed by selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns (Fig.4 and Fig.5). The SAED patterns can be used to get the distance between the crystal planes to index the crystal structure. ZrB₂ had a hexagonal symmetry with a [1-210] zone axis is observed from Fig.4.

The SAED pattern obtained from SiC grain is indexed as 15R-SiC in Fig.5. The lattice parameters of 15R-SiC are $a=3.06 \text{ \AA}$ and $c=37.07 \text{ \AA}$. And the structure of 15R-SiC has an ABCACBCABACABCBA sequence. The small spots between the diffraction spots indicate the presence of staking faults in the 15R-SiC.

Fig.4. SAED pattern of ZrB₂ grain with a [1-210] zone axis.

Fig.5. SAED pattern of SiC grain with the structure of 15R-SiC

The formation of streaks in SiC grains is due to extrinsic stacking faults (Fig.1). The high density of stacking faults in the grain is attributed to the very low stacking fault energy of SiC [10].

Moreover, some dislocations originated from grains boundaries and cross the grains were observed in the ZrB₂ grains in Fig.6. In addition, many stress patterns with bright/dark alternating contrasts are always observed in the grains (Fig.7). The formation of all the defects is caused by the residual stress in the grains, which is generated during the cooling process due to the thermal expansion coefficient mismatch between ZrB₂ ($6.8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$) and SiC ($4.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$) [16]. The

shrinkage rate of ZrB_2 is larger than that of SiC. The residual stresses for the ZrB_2 matrix and SiC particles in the composite are tensile stress and compressive stress, respectively. Sometimes, the tensile stress could promote crack growth, which may lead to low fracture toughness. However, the residual compressive stress can cause a slight improvement in fracture resistance since the propagating crack tends to avoid such compressive stress regions. Some researches have been done to design the stress distribution in the materials in order to improve the fracture toughness [12].

Fig.6. TEM micrograph of ZrB_2 grain with many dislocations

Fig.7. TEM micrograph of ZrB_2 grain with stress patterns

3.2 Microstructure of ZrB_2 -SiC-graphite

Fig.8 and Fig.9 show the morphologies of graphite in the ZrB_2 -SiC-G composite. Fig.8 shows the side face of the graphite flake, which is characterized by a long and narrow white area. Because of the small atomic number of carbon, the graphite flake is brighter than other grains. The other grains with high hardness show convex polygons. The surface of graphite flake is shown in Fig.5 (represented by G).

Fig.8. the side face of the graphite flake in ZSG

Fig.9 the surface of the graphite flake in ZSG

In the hot-pressing process, the graphite flake is bent by the force of other grains (Fig.8), which can

alleviate thermal stress caused by the thermal expansion mismatch. The thermal residual stresses between the phases could be evaluated by Hsueh's formula:

$$\sigma = \frac{(\alpha_m - \alpha_g)\Delta T}{\frac{1 + \nu_m}{(1 + \nu_g) E_m} + \frac{(1 - 2\nu_g)}{E_g}}$$

Where σ is the thermal residual stress, α is the thermal expansion coefficient, ν is the Poisson's ratio, E is Young's modulus, and ΔT is the temperature change. For the ZSG composites, $E_{ZrB_2}=490\text{GPa}$, $E_{SiC}=550\text{GPa}$, $E_g=15\text{GPa}$; $\nu_{ZrB_2}=0.17$, $\nu_{SiC}=0.14$, $\nu_g=0.25$; $\alpha_{ZrB_2}=6.8\times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$, $\alpha_{SiC}=4.7\times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$, $\alpha_g=1.5\times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$ [19, 20]. according to Hsueh's formula, the thermal residual stresses at ZrB₂-graphite and SiC-graphite interfaces (0.3GPa and 0.18GPa, respectively) were small than 1.23GPa at ZrB₂ and SiC interface. There were less dislocations can be seen in Fig.8 than that in Fig.1.

Fig.9 shows uneven edge of graphite flake. The bent graphite flake and its uneven edge indicate that the graphite flakes fill the intergranular porosities, which improves the densification of ZrB₂-based composite. The relative density and fracture toughness of the two composites reported in literatures are list in table 1.

Table 1 The relative density and fracture toughness of ZS and ZSG in the literature

	Fracture toughness (MPa m ^{1/2})[4]	Relative density (%)
ZrB ₂ -SiC	4. 0~4.5 ²	97.7 [17]
ZrB ₂ -SiC-G	6.1 ±0.4	99.7 [4]

The graphite flake is a soft phase and easily bent, so that the graphite can alleviate thermal stress of the other grains around the graphite flake. Fig.8 shows fewer defects in the grains around the bent graphite flake, which can improve the mechanical properties.

According to the molecular structure of graphite, the carbon atoms are bonded into hexagonal sheets by covalent bonding, and the layers are bonded by weak van der Waals forces. When the cracks interact with the graphite flake, deflections are observed along the surface of the graphite flake. Fig.10 shows the fractured surface of ZrB₂-SiC-graphite based on SEM. The dark long graphite flakes with 1-2 μm in thickness and ~15 μm in length can be seen. The large graphite flakes reveal that the flakes were pull out during the fracture process due

to the strong covalent bonds, which may causes crack bridging.

Fig.10 SEM image of fractured surface of ZSG

Because of the bent graphite flake, cracks propagation may require more energy. Therefore, the crack bridging and deflection improve the fracture toughness. The fracture toughness of ZrB₂-SiC-graphite composite increased by approximately 35% compared to the ZrB₂-SiC composite [4].

4. Conclusions

The microstructure of ZrB₂-SiC and ZrB₂-SiC-graphite were characterized by Transmission and analytical electron microscopy (TEM), which is a very helpful characterization tool for understanding the ceramic microstructures. Many stacking faults were found in SiC grains through TEM due to the low stacking fault energy. What is more, some dislocations and stress patterns were also observed in ZrB₂ grains in the ZrB₂-SiC composite.

From the morphologies of ZrB₂-SiC-graphite composite by TEM, we find that the bent and uneven edge of the graphite flake which caused the stress relaxation around the graphite flake can improve the densification and the mechanical properties of ZrB₂-SiC composites. Therefore, the use of graphite flake is favorable for the mechanical properties ZrB₂-based composite.

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